

„THE ROLE OF COMMUNICATION IN YOUNG CHILDREN AND ITS IMPACT ON SPEECH DEVELOPMENT”

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17366229>

Abstract. This article highlights the importance of the communication process in young children, its impact on speech development, and methods for developing communication during logopedic sessions. Communication is analyzed as a key factor in the formation of the child's personality, their adaptation to the social environment, and the development of their speech culture. The research reveals effective methods used in logopedic practice, as well as the importance of parental involvement, supported by practical examples. Recommendations and advice are provided to parents. Scholars who have studied the psychology of young children are mentioned, making this article useful and effective not only for professionals interested in the field of logopedics but also for parents. The article examines the role of communication in the formation of the child's personality, the ability to form and express thoughts, the development of communication in logopedic practice, as well as the significance of individual approaches and their practical application in reducing the lack of communication in young children.

Keywords. Communication, speech development, logopedics, child psychology, social environment, speech culture. **Introduction.** In the early years of a child's life, communication plays a central role in their mental, intellectual, and social development.

Introduction. Especially between the ages of 2 and 6, communication is vital in shaping the child's thinking, emotions, and speech. As L.S. Vygotsky emphasized, "communication is the most important bridge between a child's thinking and social experience." Therefore, a communication culture established at a young age plays an incomparable role not only in speech development but also in the child's self-awareness as a personality. In modern logopedics, communication-based approaches hold a special place. This is because speech deficiencies in children are often linked to a lack of communication or an incorrect communication environment. Thus, establishing continuous cooperation among the speech therapist, educator, and parents is one of the most essential conditions for forming a healthy speech environment for the child.

Main Part. Communication allows the child to comprehend the outside world, form thoughts, and express them. Young children expand their vocabulary through conversation, questions and answers, play, and observation. According to psychologist J. Piaget, the child assimilates social experience during the communication process and learns to express their opinion. Conversely, a lack of communication reduces the child's verbal activity, which later leads to difficulties in pronunciation and logical thinking. For sufficient communication, it is important to engage in natural conversations, read fairy tales, sing songs, and exchange ideas through play with the child throughout the day. It is precisely in these processes that the child learns to express themselves freely. Various interactive methods are used in logopedic practice

to develop communication. The following methods yield effective results: Organizing conversation through play. Play facilitates the child's natural entry into communication. For example, games like "Who is speaking?" or "Who am I?" activate speech. Role-playing games. The child tries themselves in different roles, which teaches them to express emotions and be active in communication. Creating a story based on a picture. The child describes the events depicted in the picture, expanding their vocabulary and developing logical thinking.

Parental involvement. When the child repeats the words and sounds learned in the logopedic session at home, the result is consolidated faster. Experience shows that in sessions where parents actively participate, the child's speech recovery rate is 25–30 percent higher. The link between the social environment and speech culture. The child's speech culture is closely connected to the social environment they live in. The child shapes their speech by imitating the tone, pronunciation, and speech culture of adults. Therefore, speech therapists, educators, and parents should pay special attention to speech culture. Communicating in clean, literary language directly and positively influences the child's speech. Speech disorders in a child increase due to the social environment, so it is of great importance that the child's communication is correctly ordered from a young age. Preschool age (3-7 years) is a period when the child's speech develops quickly and intensively, during which the child interacts with the environment, parents, family members, and friends. The development processes are particularly intense in 5-year-old children. At this age, they take their first steps towards school readiness. Children at this age become curious and ask questions about everything. Their capacity for assimilation increases. The education and upbringing given to children at this age remain with them until their death. Examples include: "Mommy, what is this?", "What can I do with this?", "What color is this?" and so on. In such cases, the task of adults is to patiently explain and introduce the surrounding world. Indifference, inattention, and apathy lead to negative consequences, such as developmental delays in children, underdeveloped cognitive functions, inability to express their thoughts independently, shyness, and inability to engage in discussion with peers. Not only at this age, but also during the process of talking with a baby, the child reacts to the person they are communicating with. If you smile, they smile; if your tone of voice changes, their lip curls. As they grow up, their interest in exploring the environment increases. A child is expected to know 200–300 words at 1 year old, 300–400 words at 2 years old, 1000–1200 words at 3 years old, and 2500–3000 words at 5 years old. Research suggests that the fetus senses and hears external words and emotional states from the 18th week in the womb. Therefore, young mothers are advised not to stress during pregnancy. Sources even indicate that a mother who frequently read fairy tales, talked, and established contact with her child during pregnancy positively influenced the child's rapid development and emotional state. Cognitive development, thinking, and perception functions begin to develop rapidly in young children. They start exploring objects in the environment. They become interested in and study the shape, color, type, etc., of objects. They begin to learn all the letters of the language.

Conclusion. Developing communication in young children is a necessary process for the child's speech, emotional, and social formation. Through communication, the child learns to express their thoughts, listen to the interlocutor, and adapt to the social environment. Using communication-based approaches in logopedic sessions, and the active participation of parents in these sessions, stimulates speech development in the child and creates a healthy communication environment. As a result, the child's speech perfection and mental perception are enhanced. The active involvement of parents in the sessions is of great importance.

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